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Tender Teaching in ‘Hard’ Sciences? – Fostering Gender and Diversity Skills in Engineering Education in Online Teaching and Learning in Pandemic Times

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ABSTRACT

Gender and diversity competencies are now highly valued in engineering. Various studies show that gender and diversity competencies not only help prevent exclusion and discrimination, but furthermore promote successful and sustainable engineering by prohibiting "I-methodology" and masculine professional culture. But when it comes to teaching gender and diversity topics, it becomes apparent that time and space for critical and reflective learning are critical to ensure learning success. While it is already difficult to install critical and reflective learning spaces in face-to-face classes, it becomes even more difficult in online classes. That online teaching should not be seen as a barrier to teaching gender and diversity issues, but can also bring about more accessible and caring teaching practices, is the main argument of my paper. Therefore, I will bring into focus how it is possible to create critical and reflective spaces in online teaching and learning and what teaching methodology promotes understanding of gendered matters and meanings of technology. To support the argument, I will present a range of successful online teaching of gender and diversity competencies in engineering education based on participant observation and evaluation in interdisciplinary learning settings at the Technische Universität Berlin.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Gender and diversity in engineering education

Gender and diversity competencies are now seen as very valuable in engineering. It is becoming increasingly clear that the technology-driven society needs engineers who are able to understand the social and ethical dimensions of technological problems and critically reflect on their own situatedness. Major international

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organizations such as the American Society for Engineering Education (ASEE) and the European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI) are calling for gender and diversity issues to be reflected in engineering practices and curricula in order to eliminate discrimination and marginalization based on gender and other social inequality structures [1].

Feminist STS has shed light on the fact that if we are serious about the goal of making engineering education sensitive to gender and diversity issues, engineering students need more than a brief dive into inequality and diversity issues to be able to advance technological solutions to highly complex social situations in the future [2]. To this end, engineering education should strive to broaden and deepen students' understanding of social power dynamics by teaching them about the deeply gendered constitution of technology and offering them knowledge about how gender and other power relations become material. Gender and diversity competencies not only help to prevent exclusion and discrimination, but also promote successful and sustainable engineering by prohibiting "I-methodology" and masculine professional culture [3]. It also promotes the acceptance of gender and diversity issues in general and satisfies the desire of students to look beyond their own discipline, as well as providing the opportunity to learn how to reflect on ethical issues in engineering and design processes [4].

1.2 Gender and diversity issues as irritating and uneasy learning material

When it comes to teaching gender and diversity topics, time and space for critical and reflective learning are critical to ensure a successful learning process and to develop research-based gender competencies [5]. While it is already difficult to install critical and reflective learning spaces in face-to-face classes, it becomes even more complicated in online classes, especially during a global pandemic.

Learning about gender and diversity has been described as a difficult learning process that requires students to leave their affective and epistemic comfort zones by being irritated by the change in their perspective and thereby learning to critically reflect on their presupposed beliefs [6]. Therefore, it is critical to design a learning environment that provides a comfortable and safe space. This is especially important in times of pandemic, when teachers and learners face the burden of increased care work and precarity.

2 METHODOLOGY

In the following, I present successful online teaching on gender and diversity in engineering education based on a qualitative research design at the Center for Interdisciplinary Women's and Gender Studies (ZIFG) at the Technische Universität Berlin (TU Berlin).

The observed courses were all conducted online by the author in the winter term 2020/2021 and the summer term 2021 at the ZIFG of the TU Berlin. The participant observations were mainly conducted during the courses. The evaluation took place in the last course of the semester. In four courses students gave oral feedback (in

total 31 statements) and in one course students handed in written feedback via online chat. Thereby only 12 out of 20 students gave feedback. The feedback and observations were analyzed using Mayring's content analysis [8].

The general focus of the courses was on developing research-based gender competencies to support students' agency in gender-sensitive and diversity-oriented action. Students also learned to apply empirical methods to research on gender and diversity or to develop understanding of intersectional forms of discrimination and co-constructive processes of gendering artifacts. Courses included topics such as feminist philosophy and critique of science and technology, transdisciplinarity of gender studies of science and technology, gender in higher education, and empirical methods in gender studies. Participants came from various fields of Engineering, Biotechnology, Computation and Design, and Culture and Technology, as well as Gender Studies. The courses were attended by a total of 51 students. For synchronous sessions, the video conferencing tool Zoom, specified by the TU Berlin, was used. The asynchronous sessions were prepared and conducted via an e-learning platform.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Applying a tender teaching methodology to online classroom

In developing an instructional design for teaching online in an interdisciplinary learning environment during a global pandemic, I was guided by feminist scholarship as it seemed to be a rich source of knowledge on how to construct a more equitable and enjoyable, as well as safe, learning environment that would enable students to acquire critical and reflective knowledge about gender and diversity issues.

Bell hooks' concept of engaged pedagogy, in particular, emphasizes the need to activate students and practice "free speech, dissent, and pluralistic opinions" [9]. It also emphasizes the importance of a trusting "interactive relationship between student and teacher" [10] that should enable students to experience learning with joy as an active and pleasurable process. Likewise, Becky Thompson's concept of teaching with tenderness brings in the goal of "keeping more complexity, paradox, and community in mind" [11] by simultaneously emphasizing the embodied dimensions of learning processes. This connection to the more affective and emotional, as well as material, sides of learning is very important as online learning transforms classroom relationships between teachers and learners, and between learners and learners, into more distanced encounters [12].

Therefore, the main focus in the design of the teaching concept was on supporting a trusting learning culture and avoiding feelings of acceleration and exhaustion [13] in online learning. Early on, a culture of kindness and friendliness was implemented by indicating in the syllabus that students were expected to be kind to each other and that failures would be tolerated. Furthermore, students were regularly encouraged to contact me with questions or problems. Introductory rounds were integrated to give time to get to know each other. In addition, the opportunity for students to discuss in small groups was offered on a regular basis. After each group work, students were

given time to present their findings in a joint plenary discussion. In order to make the seminars more accessible to working professionals or people with caregiving responsibilities, the seminars were held on a biweekly schedule for synchronous sessions. I also always strove to maintain a teaching attitude that appropriately acknowledged the achievements made in the seminar. A dose of humor additionally contributed to a pleasant course culture when the internet connection broke down, people got lost in online rooms, or children, pets, and parents showed up.

3.2 Tender teaching as a way to further research-based gender competencies

Participant observations clearly showed that applying a tender teaching methodology promotes commitment to online courses. During the term, student's knowledge of gender and diversity developed impressively. Students in all five different courses appeared to be highly motivated, engaged in attentive discussion, and ultimately were able to translate complex topics into their disciplinary knowledge. They behaved very respectfully, avoided interrupting each other, and listened extremely attentively. Some students even felt comfortable enough to share personal stories or talk about their insights and inclinations related to the course content.

Many students also explicitly praised the seminar atmosphere in their feedback, which had supported them well in understanding the topics. One student wrote: "I thought it was good that we had so much time and that you, [author], led the seminar in a very calm, determined and yet time-giving manner. Gender studies is a personally emotional topic for many of those who take part in it, and it requires a lot of sensitivity with all speakers." (Feedback_1). 40 out of 43 students stated in their final feedbacks that they were satisfied with their learning outcomes on the complexity of gender, diversity, technology and empirical methods. Also, biweekly schedule was regarded by 40 out of 43 students as very helpful for cruising the obstacles of studying online while in the midst of a pandemic. Two male students stated that course culture and concept had very much supported them mentally over the winter term.

4. SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The feedback evaluations and participant observations made it clear that students' ability to critically reflect on gender and diversity issues in engineering and technology in online learning thrived through a teaching methodology that focused on engaging pedagogy and the concept of teaching with tenderness. Due to the fact that the pandemic tends to affect the mental health of students, the use of a slower and more tender yet effective teaching methodology could help develop an enjoyable and safe learning environment and in this way support student learning. Online instruction, therefore, should not be seen as a barrier to teaching gender and diversity issues, but rather as a way to promote and implement more accessible and caring teaching methods. The initial results of implementing this teaching method are promising and should be explored further.

I would like to acknowledge the impressive engagement of students in the online seminars despite any obstacles due to Covid-19.

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